

Road construction impact assessment

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Abstract

Environmental safety of highways is achieved by developing and applying technical solutions in project documents for construction, reconstruction, repair and maintenance.

Key words: social, landscape, AMTB, exploitation, engineering. construction, reconstruction, repair, maintenance.

Абстракт

Экологическая безопасность автомобильных дорог достигается путем разработки и применения технических решений в проектной документации на строительство, реконструкцию, ремонт и содержание.

Ключевые слова: социальные, ландшафт, ОВОС, эксплуатационные, инженер. строительство, реконструкция, ремонт, техническое обслуживание.

Limiting the negative impact on the environment to an acceptable level, which does not result in harmful consequences for public health, irreversible changes in the natural environment, or deterioration of the socio-economic living conditions of people. During the implementation of project documents, it is necessary to comply with the established rules on environmental management and environmental protection (On environmental impact assessment during the design, construction, reconstruction and use of road objects instruction, 2001. No. os-482-r).

The main method of determining the level of environmental safety of technical or organizational decisions is environmental impact assessment, which includes the analysis of the environmental situation, determining the composition and nature of impacts and forecasting their consequences. Environmental impact assessment (EIA)

is carried out for the combination of the factors affecting the estimated (least favorable) state of the environment and the estimated useful life of the designed facility, and the significance level of all identified impacts and each significant includes determining the allowable level of the species. impact on each environmental component in the area crossed by the road. As a result of AMTB, a conclusion is made about the permissibility (or disallowance) of construction, the need to apply protective measures, and the possibility or impossibility of implementing the planned solutions.

Studies on environmental impact assessment of planned economy and other activities include:

determine the characteristics of the planned economic and other activities and possible alternatives (including the abandonment of activities);

analysis of the state of the area that may be affected by the planned farm and other activities (state of the natural environment, presence and character of anthropogenic load, etc.);

to determine the possible impact of the planned farm and other activities on the environment, taking into account alternative options;

assessment of the impact of planned economic and other activities on the environment (prediction of the probability of occurrence, level, nature, scope, distribution area, as well as environmental and socio-economic consequences related to them);

determination of measures that reduce, mitigate or prevent negative effects, evaluate their effectiveness and feasibility of implementation;

assessment of the importance of residual effects on the environment and their consequences;

a comparison of the expected environmental and associated socio-economic consequences of the considered alternatives, including the justification of the option of abandoning the activity and the option proposed for implementation;

development of proposals for environmental monitoring and control program at all stages of implementation of planned economic and other activities;

development of recommendations for conducting a post-project analysis of the implementation of planned economic and other activities;

- preparation of the preliminary version of materials on environmental impact assessment of planned economic and other activities (including summary for non-specialists).

Environmental safety assessment of highways should cover the following groups and types of impacts, differing in their sources of occurrence:

a) traffic pollution (waste) - emissions from vehicles using the road: exhaust gases, traffic noise, dust (solid) waste and wear of coatings, polluting the air, soil and water flow in the neighboring area;

b) changes in natural and economic systems as a result of the construction of the road and the engineering structures included in its complex: land acquisition, reshaping of the relief, changes in the flow, level and conditions of underground water, separation of biological systems and economic lands, existing infrastructure;

c) technological effects during construction or other works: pollution of the atmosphere, soil and water bodies during the operation of road vehicles, industrial noise, dust dispersion, temporary occupation, land pollution.

The main objects of the impact of highways on the environment are natural and socio-economic components (Table 8).

Table 8 Characteristics of objects affected by highways
(Instructions on environmental impact assessment in the design, construction, reconstruction and operation of road facilities, 2001 y. No os-482-r)

Group	Component	Indicators
	Air	Pollution with gases, dust, noise level, microclimate
	Water resources	Surface flows, reservoirs, groundwater pollution, changes in groundwater levels

	Land resources, soil	Stability of soil masses, resistance to erosion, productivity of the soil layer
	Biological resources	Plants, animals land, water environment, agricultural production

Socio-economic	Living conditions of the population	Sanitary, psychological parameters
	Economic interests of society and individuals	Economic development opportunities, jobs, saving lives
	Land use	Uy-joy, qishloq xo'jaligi, o'rmon xo'jaligi, dam olish, dacha xo'jaligi), sanoat va boshqa korxonalarining joylashuvi
	Transport infrastructure	Ijtimoiy ob'ektlarning mavjudligi, mavjud aloqalar tizimini saqlab qolish
	Objects of scientific and spiritual importance	Historical and cultural monuments, archaeological sites, protected areas, natural phenomena
	Landscape aesthetics	Natural, cultural, urbanized

Conclusion

Limiting the negative impact on the environment to an acceptable level, which does not result in harmful consequences for public health, irreversible changes in the natural environment, or deterioration of the socio-economic living conditions of people. During the implementation of project documents, it is necessary to comply with the established rules on environmental management and environmental protection (On environmental impact assessment during the design, construction, reconstruction and use of road objects guide, 2001. No os-482-r).

LIST OF LITERATURE:

1. Abdulxayev Javoxir Jaxongir o'g'li (2024) Loyihalashtirilgan yo'llarning xususiyatlari va ekologik va iqtisodiy ekspress yo'l qurish ob'ektlarini taqqoslash. "Xavfsizlik va atrof-muhitni muhofaza qilish muammolarini hal qilishda fan va ta'limning ro'li" mavzusidagi respublika ilmiy-amaliy anjumani, 476-481.

2. Abdulxayev Javoxir Jaxongir o'g'li (2024) Avto yo'lning atrof-muhitga ta'siri. "Xavfsizlik va atrof-muhitni muhofaza qilish muammolarini hal qilishda fan va ta'limning ro'li" mavzusidagi respublika ilmiy-amaliy anjumani, 459-463.

3. Abdulxayev Javoxir Jaxongir o'g'li (2023) History and formation of the fergana valley agricultural system of environmental management. Scientific and Technical Journal of NamIET, 531-526.

4. Abdulxayev, Javoxir. (2023) Oziq-ovqat chiqindilarini qayta ishlash uchun sm (samarali mikroorganizmlar) texnologiyasi. *Theoretical aspects in the formation of pedagogical sciences*, 2 (13), 71-74.

5. Абдулхаев, Ж. Ж., (2023) Воздействие экотуризма на природу. *GOLDEN BRAIN*, 1(15), 156-160.

6. Декоративные деревья и кустарники с фитоцитарными свойствами и способы их размножения. ЖЖУ Абдулхаев, СС Абдурахмонов, (2022) *Science and innovation* 1 (D2), 71-74.

7. Использование декоративных медоносных растений. укрепление кормовой базы для пчеловодств. А Тохтабоев, Ж Абдулхаев (2022) Экономика и социум, 679-681.

8. Farg'ona vodiysini rivojlanish tarixi va shakllanish omillari atrof-muhitni boshqarishning qishloq xojaligi tizimi. Abdulxayev, Javoxir. (2023) Ijodkor o'qituvchi ilmiy-uslubiy jurnal.

9. Maishiy chiqindilarni qayta ishlash va muqobil energiya manbalarini olish. Abdulxayev, Javoxir. (2023)